

PHBV FORMULATION AND COMPOUNDING

VISS
INFO PACK
N. 02

From food industry residues to bio-based packaging, the ViSS approach connects feedstock conditioning, fermentation and optimisation, green solvent extraction, and final material transformation into a circular solution.

Discover part of the value chain in this info pack.

THE VISS VALUE CHAIN: MID-STEPS

Poly(3-hydroxybutyrate-co-3-hydroxyvalerate) (PHBV) is a good biopolymer candidate for circular packaging options. It is a copolymer derived from poly(3-hydroxybutyrate) (PHB) with 3-hydroxyvalerate (3HV) units. PHBV is available commercially, in grades containing only 1–2% of 3HV comonomer content. It has good mechanical properties but suffers from a narrow processing window and degradation.

Within ViSS, research focuses on improving the long-term stability of PHBV through controlled copolymer composition, polymer blending and the inclusion of additives based on **Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD) principles**. Increasing the 3HV content results in reduced crystallinity, enhanced flexibility, toughness and impact resistance. This brings the properties of PHBV closer to those of conventional petroleum-based plastics, while maintaining a strong sustainability profile. **ViSS aims to produce PHBV with 10 to 30% of 3HV content.**

DESCRIPTION OF THE PROCESS

Commercial PHBV with 1–2% 3HV comonomer content, is prone to:

- **Thermal degradation** is close to its melting point, causing molecular weight loss during melt processing.
- **Low crystal nucleation density**, leading to brittleness and slow processing cycles.
- **Secondary crystallisation**, which induces embrittlement during storage.
- **Limited flexibility**, reducing applicability in thin films and food contact materials.

PHBV formulation development within ViSS combines computational screening, experimental validation, and compounding trials to identify effective, food-safe property modifiers.

TECHNICAL POINTS

Hydrogen bonding and control of crystallisation

Hydrogen-bonding interactions can either promote nucleation (orotic acid, theobromine) or hinder growth of the crystalline structures (glucose, ascorbic acid).

Predictive simulation-guided formulation

Molecular dynamics provides quantitative insight into additive loading effects on T_g and polymer dynamics, supporting efficient experimental design.

Processing-structure balance

Orotic acid maintains mechanical integrity while improving crystallisation effect on the VISS PHBV with higher comonomer content.

Safe and sustainable additive framework

All proposed modifiers comply with food-contact safety standards and align with Safe and Sustainable by Design principles.

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